

Artificial Intelligence and Possible Futures: Insights from an Exploratory Survey

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Statements and Declarations

Author Contributions

The authors adhere to an adapted version of the CRediT author statement (Allen, O'Connell, and Kiermer 2019) to recognise individual contributions:

Raquel Ribeiro: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data analysis, Visualisation, Supervision, Writing - Original Draft, and Revision.

Filipe Santos: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, and Revision.

Ana Teixeira de Melo: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing- Review & Editing, Supervision, project administration

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Andreia Sofia Teixeira: Methodology

Leo Caves: Methodology, Writing- Review & Editing

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Paula Duarte Lopes: Methodology

Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Centre for Social Studies Research Ethics Committee (approval no. 084_24) on July 25, 2024.

Consent to participate

Respondents gave written informed consent before starting to answer the survey.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Declaration of conflicting interest

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

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Data availability

Data is available at XXX

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Abstract

The world is facing fast and profound societal transformations that challenge our constructions of reality. Developments in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) raise the need to tackle these complex challenges. However, misinformation and disinformation about AI (and generated by AI itself) pose one of the major global risks for the future. An online survey was applied to study public opinion on AI. Two main opinion clusters were found: Supporters that associate AI with technological optimism; Critics that stress the degradation of social and human values. These groups also differ in the level of trust in political institutions responsible for regulating AI and its impacts. There is a need to stimulate public discussion about the potential impacts of AI as well as the role of institutions in its regulation.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; public opinion; positive and negative impacts; trust; regulation

Introduction

The field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has seen rapid development in recent years. Both the academic literature and everyday media discourses on AI are divided between those adhering to an optimistic stance and claiming its potential benefits, and those highlighting potential dangers and the implications for the organisation of society and its practices, in a variety of domains, from work to education, to health management and policy-making (Carrasco et al., 2019).

Some developments in the field of AI have been explored in relation to the need to tackle complex challenges and to generate social good. As stated by Cows and collaborators (2021: 114) “designed well, AI technologies can foster the delivery of socially good outcomes with unprecedented scale and efficiency”. Recent advances in AI have facilitated access to, management of, and interaction with, vast amounts of information, in ways that may, under certain conditions, contribute to building complex knowledge (Heyman et al., 2024).

Large language models (LLMs) from the field of machine learning (ML), a sub-branch of AI, are statistical models (varieties of artificial neural networks, ANN) of the associations between words (in general tokens) built from large text corpora, like books, papers, web pages, and social media (OpenAI, 2023). A milestone in LLMs came in November 2022 with the public release of ChatGPT (Chat tool based on Generative Pre-trained Transformer LLM) developed by OpenAI, designed to produce text in response to user questions. Its output is broadly accepted to be of a quality close to text produced by a human. This tool (originally based on GPT v3.5), using the largest training dataset to date,

and including some human fine-tuning, crossed a threshold of acceptance/utility with users, and has (along with other similar tools) become very popular. Ushering in the (latest) era of AI promise, offering new possibilities for human AI-Interaction (Roumeliotis and Tselikas, 2023). The capacities of this model, including its ability to adapt to context, enable an intuitive type of communication through human-like text (Roumeliotis and Tselikas, 2023). The developments in the field have rapidly expanded the number of LLMs that vary in training, design, and purposes (e.g. Claude, Gemini and Llama).

Generative AI can create novel content that is not just text. Other tools (e.g. DALL-E, Dreamfusion, Codex, Midjourney) are capable of creatively working not only with text but converting text to image, audio, video, code or vice-versa (Gozalo-Brizuela and Garrido-Merchán, 2023); increasingly these different capabilities are being incorporated into single “multi-modal” tools. Increasing realistic AI content from such tools has contributed to the spreading of malicious “deepfakes”, and the growing sophistication of bots using these models, raises concerns about the difficulty for the average user to distinguish between human and machine generated content (Gambín et al., 2024).

AI models pose different types of challenges and risks (Saghiri et al., 2022). Concerns have been raised about the implications of a widespread use of these tools, for example, in relation to teaching or academic production (Castellanos-Gomez, 2023; Romero-Rodríguez et al., 2023; Susnjak, 2022). Ethical issues have also been raised (Ray, 2023; Zhuo, 2023), for example regarding data privacy and security, authorship, bias and fairness, transparency, misuse and even abuse, influence on human decision-making, amongst others. Goar et al. (2023) list limitations such as: lack of ‘common sense’ and inability to make decisions based on it; limited understanding of context (although this is an area of significant advance); bias in training data; difficulty understanding complex questions and reasoning; lack of creativity; difficulty in understanding emotions and in abstracting concepts, leading to inaccurate responses. It also has difficulty in dealing with ambiguity and maintaining context of a conversation (Ray, 2023).

A variety of factors that affect the acceptance of AI have been identified, including perceived usefulness, fairness, attitudes, trust, effort expectancy or cultural factors, experience, and facilitating conditions (Kelly et al., 2023; Romero-Rodríguez et al., 2023), which are influenced by media discourses (Roe and Perkins, 2023).

Public perceptions of AI reflect a variety of perspectives and facets, from optimism and confidence to skepticism and doubt, about technological development, tech developers, and the consequences for the future of humankind. Optimism is based on the promises of improvement of daily life and human abilities, while concerns arise from issues such as autonomy, unintended consequences, and how these developments might impact economic disparities, and worsen human relations (Pew Research Center, 2022). Evaluations and expectations differ considerably between domains of application (Brauner et al., 2023).

A survey of the US public’s perceptions and beliefs about the governance of AI suggested preferences for a bottom-up, human centred approach to the development and regulation of AI, and found that different levels of social trust determine the willingness to accept governance from various stakeholders, namely governments, technology corporations, or individual citizens (David et al., 2024). Perceived trust in social structures and agencies can be associated with polarized emotions. Hughes (2024), develops an analysis of the role of

emotions in the construction of imagined futures to conclude that, although their capacity to affect change is not evident, they are powerful in shaping collective representations and alternatives of sociotechnical worlds. The perception not just of practitioners in several domains and of policy/makers, but also of the ordinary citizen will shape the relation of individuals and communities on AI, its acceptance and modes of use, the dissemination of more or less positive or negative discourses, and the capacity of particular communities to have a role in regulating its use or call upon particular institutions for such a role (David et al., 2024).

Present Study

The present study is part of a broader research exploratory project analysing the potential of AI to support more complex modes of thinking in the face of current global challenges, examining the potentialities, constraints and risks of interaction of a theoretical model on complex thinking and LLM (anonymized reference). Given that the use of AI tools to scaffold more complex modes of thinking is dependent not just on the technical performance of such tools but also on how people interact with them and that these interactions may be shaped by how they perceive and represent them, this study aims to capture public opinion regarding AI and the use of AI and, in particular, explore the dimensions that are associated with optimism vs. skepticism, adherence vs. refusal

Method

Instrument and Procedure

The study was carried out through a survey composed of closed and open-ended questions, involving several domains. The first page presented the survey, guaranteed the anonymity and confidentiality of the collected information, and requested written informed consent for participation. Then, a first set of questions intended to capture the representations and positions on AI, which included a free association task with the question: “When you hear the expression ‘Artificial Intelligence’ or ‘AI’”, what words or expressions immediately come to mind?” followed by seven-point scales on binary adjectives (e.g., 1 = *Bad*; 7 = *Good*) and assessment of information (1 = *Not Informed*; 7 = *Very informed*), worry (1 = *Nothing worried*; 7 = *Very worried*), concern (1 = *It doesn't concern me at all*; 7 = *It concerns me a lot*), compelled to use (1 = *Not at all compelled*; 7 = *Very compelled*) and preparation to use AI tools (1 = *Not at all prepared*; 7 = *Totally prepared*).

A second set of questions intended to examine the opinions about the possible impacts of AI in the future of humanity (see Table 2) included several bipolar 7-point scale questions (e.g., 1 = *Increase social inequalities*; 7 = *Decrease social inequalities*) and an open question to “Describe how do you imagine the future 5 years from now and the role of Artificial Intelligence in that future”.

To examine opinions about the use of AI, namely acceptability, trust and knowledge, several questions were presented: a) Two sets of questions (see Table 3) examined the level of acceptability of different uses (e.g., *Disease screening and diagnosis*), and the possibility of use and trust in the information produced on different domains (e.g., *To help with a professional problem*); b) Two sets of questions evaluated the level of knowledge and

experience (1=*I've never heard about it*; 2= *I have heard about it, but I have never used it*; 3=*I have used it sometimes*; 4=*I have used it quite a lot or many times*) about several AI tools (e.g., *Chat GPT*; *Claude*); c) Payment (yes vs. no) for a subscription for using AI tools; d) Purposes for which used AI (e.g., *work, education, health*); e) Open question “*Of the things you have done using Artificial Intelligence, tell us about the one that you consider to be the most interesting*”.

The perceived need for preparation/specialised education and regulation was evaluated through 7-point scales (1= *Not at all necessary*, 7 = *Totally necessary*; 1= *No need for regulation*, 7 = *There is a need for regulation*). Participants were also asked about their level of trust (1 = *No trust*; 7 = *Full trust*) on different institutions (e.g., European political institutions, Tech companies) to regulate AI as well as in people in general/self-regulation.

Subsequently, the questionnaire included several questions to explore the psychosocial dimensions associated with representations and opinions about AI. These concerned several domains: a) the *emotions elicited by AI* (see Appendix 2) as well as the assessment of threat vs. opportunity for different targets (e.g., the younger generations; poor and developing countries); b) the *salience of the theme*, evaluated by the frequency of talk about AI (1=*Very rarely*; 7=*Every day*), and the domains of conversation accessed by an open question asking to describe the most interesting conversation; c) the *expertise in the use of AI*, electronics and the internet in general (1=*Inexperienced user/ without knowledge*; 7=*Advanced/highly specialised user*); d) the *dimensions valued* (1=*I do not value at all*; 7=*I totally value*) in the assessment of the information people are confronted with (e.g., the presentation is rich in details); e) *level of agreement* (1 = *Totally disagree*; 7 = *Totally agree*) with a set of statements about society - referring to anomie, system justification, and legal cynicism-, as well as agreement with principles of distributive justice (equality, equity and need); and f) *Sociodemographic characterization* (e.g., gender, age, education, occupational situation, financial situation, nationality, access to equipments).

The construction of the instrument involved a first stage of elaboration and selection of relevant questions according to literature review. The survey was administered in two languages (English and Portuguese). Subsequently, to assess understanding of the instructions, questions and answer options and test their sequence, pre-tests were carried out in both versions. Before data collection, the final version was submitted and received approval by the ethics review board of [name of research centre blinded for review] (REF 90/24).

Data collection took place between August 6 to October 21, 2024, through a non-probabilistic sampling. The survey was fully administered online using the Limesurvey tool (LimeSurvey GmbH, 2021). A snowball strategy was used to disseminate the survey as well as collaboration requests via emails to various institutions (e.g., universities, municipal and parish councils, non-profit associations of different natures).

Participants

The survey received responses from 383 individuals, and 248 met the inclusion criteria for the present study (answering at least 80% of the questions of all the questions). More than half of the respondents were female (65.3%, 32.7% male and 2.0% non-binary) with a mean age of 47.96 years ($SD = 11.95$). The majority resided in Portugal (87.5%) at the

time of the survey while 12.5% lived in other countries (e.g., 2.8% in UK, 2.8% in the USA, 2% in Brazil, and 1.2% in Italy). The majority (75.9%) had a higher education degree, of which 36.3% a BA, 19.4% a Masters, and 20.2% a PhD, and worked for an employer with a permanent contract (77.0%). For a full sociodemographic characterization of the study sample see Appendix 1.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated for closed item questions; missing answers needed for multivariate analysis were replaced by group means. To identify groups of respondents differing on their opinion about AI, we performed a hierarchical cluster analysis using Ward's method to measure the squared Euclidean distance for the variables listed in Table 1. The decision on the number of clusters was taken from the resulting dendrogram. The inclusion of the subjects in each cluster was obtained with the application of the non-hierarchical K-Means procedure. To assess the differences between clusters on the different dimensions in analysis (e.g., impacts, use), several *t-test* analyses were performed, with the cluster membership as the independent variable. Chi-square tests were also performed in order to check whether cluster membership was independent from socio-demographic variables.

The words evoked were recorded in a data file applying the reduction rules generally used in free task associations, which also aggregated some obvious synonyms (cf. Ribeiro and Poeschl, 2020). The evoked terms were analysed and the frequency of their association to the different clusters was compared by means of the Chi-square statistic. All statistical analyses were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics software (v. 29).

Results and Discussion

Positions and Representations concerning AI

Overall, on average, participants in the survey tend to consider AI as useful, accessible, sustainable, good, pleasant, and beautiful, highlighting a slightly positive attitude. However, participants also tend to consider AI more dishonest than honest (see Table 1). Following this trend, participants tend to view AI as a matter of concern but feel slightly compelled to use it. They perceive themselves somewhat informed about AI, albeit unprepared.

To identify groups of respondents differing in their opinion about AI, we performed a hierarchical cluster analysis using Ward's method. The dendrogram produced suggested the presence of two clusters. Table 1 presents the number of respondents classified in each cluster, obtained through the application of k-means clustering ($k = 2$), as well as the means and standard deviations for each variable.

Table 1. Differences in Positioning in Relation to AI. Means Based on Clusters, Standard Deviations in Parentheses.

Poles of the 7-point scales	<i>Critics</i>	<i>Supporters</i>	Total	<i>t</i>	Cohen's <i>d</i>
	(n=117)	(n=131)	(N=248)	sig	

Bad-Good	3.37	5.31	4.39	-14.21	1.07
	(1.14)	(1.00)	(1.44)	***	
Unsustainable-Sustainable	3.51	5.37	4.50	-11.45	1.26
	(1.41)	(1.11)	(1.57)	***	
Negative-Positive	3.28	5.33	4.37	-14.74	1.09
	(1.14)	(1.05)	(1.50)	***	
Ugly-Beautiful	3.45	4.97	4.26	-10.26	1.17
	(1.17)	(1.16)	(1.39)	***	
Unpleasant-Pleasant	3.32	5.18	4.30	-13.95	1.05
	(1.13)	(0.98)	(1.41)	***	
Dishonest-Honest	2.88	4.60	3.79	-11.63	1.16
	(1.12)	(1.20)	(1.44)	***	
Useless-Useful	4.50	6.26	5.43	-12.64	1.06
	(1.31)	(0.77)	(1.38)	***	
Inaccessible-Accessible	4.26	5.61	4.97	-8.54	1.24
	(1.40)	(1.08)	(1.41)	***	
Unfair-Fair	3.11	4.72	3.96	-11.13	1.14
	(1.06)	(1.20)	(1.39)	***	
Not Informed-Very Informed	3.50	4.68	4.13	-6.59	1.40
	(1.51)	(1.30)	(1.52)	***	
Nothing worried-Very Worried	5.61	4.76	5.16	4.77	1.40
	(1.37)	(1.43)	(1.46)	***	
It doesn't concern me at all- It concerns me a lot	4.97	5.78	5.40	-4.60	1.36
	(1.61)	(1.08)	(1.42)	***	
Not at all compelled- Very compelled	2.97	5.50	4.31	-13.81	1.43
	(1.59)	(1.27)	(1.91)	***	
Not at all prepared- Totally prepared	2.67	4.73	3.76	-11.86	1.37
	(1.43)	(1.31)	(1.71)	***	

Note: Highest means in bold; *: $p \leq 0.05$; **: $p \leq 0.01$; ***: $p \leq 0.001$

Results in Table 1 show two opposing positions regarding AI: *Critics* vs. *Supporters*. Although both consider AI as useful and accessible, and something that concerns and worries them, they differ on the degree, being the first more pessimistic. However, if Supporters tend to consider AI sustainable, positive, good, being compelled, informed and prepared to deal with AI, the Critics' cluster tends to consider it dishonest, negative, unpleasant, ugly and unsustainable.

In terms of the free association task, globally, 1027 words or expressions were collected of which 426 were unique, with a frequency of occurrence varying from 1 (316 terms) to 44 ("future"). Besides "future", the most frequent words (evoked by at least 10% of participants) also included the terms "robots" (40), "technology" (35), "innovation" (32), "fear" (30) and "computer" (25). Looking at the words evoked by each cluster (see Figure 1), while some of the associated words are similar, the Critics' cluster includes more negative terms like "fear", "danger", "falsehood", and the Supporters' cluster mostly associates AI with notions of "innovation" ($\chi^2(1) = 4.50, p < .050$), "speed" ($\chi^2(1) = 9.94, p < .010$), "help" ($\chi^2(1) = 8.33, p < .010$).

1= Increase discrimination and prejudice	2.78	4.13	3.49	-8.08	-1.35	-1.6 8	-1.0 2	-1.03
	(1.26)	(1.36)	(1.47)	***				
1= Have negative impacts in work and employment	2.66	4.70	3.74	-10.6 4	-2.04	-2.4 2	-1.6 6	-1.35
	(1.48)	(1.53)	(1.82)	***				
1= Decrease the quality of education and teaching-learning	2.87	4.48	3.72	-7.98	-1.61	-2.0 0	-1.2 1	-1.01
	(1.57)	(1.60)	(1.77)	***				
1= Weaken democracy	2.72	4.04	3.42	-8.32	-1.31	-1.6 3	-1.0 0	-1.06
	(1.23)	(1.26)	(1.40)	***				
1= Harm collective security	2.83	4.21	3.56	-7.47	-1.38	-1.7 4	-1.0 2	-0.96
	(1.53)	(1.36)	(1.60)	***				
1= Worsen the quality of public decision making	2.83	4.70	3.82	-10.6 9	-1.87	-2.2 1	-1.5 2	-1.36
	(1.37)	(1.37)	(1.66)	***				
1= Worsen the quality of human relations	2.30	3.68	3.03	-7.93	-1.38	-1.7 2	-1.0 4	-1.01
	(1.32)	(1.40)	(1.53)	***				
1= Decrease the freedom of decision by citizens	2.65	4.05	3.39	-8.07	-1.39	-1.7 3	-1.0 5	-1.03
	(1.33)	(1.39)	(1.52)	***				
1= Bring humanity to its end	3.33	4.33	3.86	-6.04	-0.99	-1.3 2	-0.6 7	-0.77
	(1.15)	(1.41)	(1.38)	***				

*: $p \leq 0.05$; **: $p \leq 0.01$; ***: $p \leq 0.001$

In relation to the open question “Please describe how you imagine the future 5 years from now and the role of Artificial Intelligence in that future”, 70.1% of Critics and 66.4% of Supporters provided descriptions. Imagined futures show a high prevalence of AI, something that will be part of daily lives. But if Supporters see themselves as riding the wave, Critics fear to be hit by it like a tsunami.

I think it will be embedded in everything we do and I hope it helps with more mechanical tasks (Supporters, 070)

There is no way to put the genie back into the bottle so I'll ride this wave (Supporters, 093)

...for the general population it will be an extension of social media and tech toys, a gimmick that few will appreciate its real value and potential, and possibly becoming a danger because of how easy it can be used by people with ill-intentions (Critics, 544)

I do not see a general preparation (...) I think it will be fully advanced in a not very distant future, and it will hit us all like a tsunami (Critics, 335)

Use of AI: Acceptability, Trust and Knowledge

When asked about the level of acceptability of different uses for AI, results in Table 3 show that the majority of the uses presented in the survey were considered unacceptable, even by Supporters, being the exception the use of AI for disease screening and diagnosis and to solve environmental problems related with climate change. Supporters also considered that it was acceptable to use AI for monitoring people for public security purposes, for financial decision-making, and had an ambivalent position for the use of AI for determination of risk

profiles by insurance companies and banks. The uses considered less acceptable were related to the media, like news production, rendering AI videos or images, and data collection for advertising. These are, most likely, the uses of AI that are closely related to the experiences of respondents.

Table 3. Uses of AI. Means Based on Clusters, Standard Deviations in Parentheses.

		Critics	Supporters	Total	<i>t</i>	Mean difference	95% CI		Cohen's <i>d</i>
		(n=117)	(n=131)	(N=248)	sig		Inf.	Sup.	
Acceptability of use (1 = <i>Totally unacceptable</i>; 7 = <i>Totally acceptable</i>)									
Disease screening and diagnosis		5.50	5.92	5.72	-1.95	-0.43	-0.86	0.00	-0.25
		(1.86)	(1.55)	(1.71)	<i>t</i>				
Military uses for offensive purposes		2.23	3.05	2.66	-3.46	-0.83	-1.30	-0.36	-0.44
		(1.72)	(2.05)	(1.94)	***				
Monitoring people for public security purposes		3.09	4.38	3.77	-5.08	-1.30	-1.80	-0.79	-0.65
		(1.97)	(2.04)	(2.10)	***				
Automatisation of Teaching		2.14	3.63	2.93	-7.04	-1.49	-1.91	-1.08	-0.88
		(1.49)	(1.84)	(1.84)	***				
Decision-making and sentencing in courts		2.01	2.72	2.39	-3.38	-0.71	-1.13	-0.30	-0.43
		(1.52)	(1.80)	(1.71)	***				
Determination of risk profiles by insurance companies and banks		2.91	4.01	3.49	-4.82	-1.10	-1.55	-0.65	-0.61
		(1.76)	(1.83)	(1.88)	***				
In the manipulation of images, videos and sounds to be publicly shared		1.59	2.00	1.81	-2.50	-0.41	-0.73	-0.09	-0.31
		(1.09)	(1.46)	(1.31)	*				
Personal data collection and processing for the personalization of contents and advertising for commercial purposes		2.07	2.67	2.39	-2.74	-0.60	-1.04	-0.17	-0.34
		(1.52)	(1.94)	(1.78)	**				
Automated production of news		1.80	2.65	2.25	-4.48	-0.85	-1.22	-0.47	-0.56
		(1.22)	(1.74)	(1.57)	***				
To solve environmental problems related to climate change		4.90	5.61	5.27	-2.93	-0.71	-1.19	-0.23	-0.38
		(2.06)	(1.72)	(1.92)	**				
Financial decision-making		2.99	4.19	3.62	-5.48	-1.20	-1.63	-0.77	-0.70
		(1.68)	(1.76)	(1.82)	***				
Possibility of Use (1 = <i>Never</i>; 7 = <i>Always</i>) and Trust in the Information (1 = <i>No trust</i>; 7 = <i>Total trust</i>)									
To gather information on a topic of interest	use	3.91	6.00	5.02	-9.93	-2.09	-2.50	-1.67	-1.31
		(2.08)	(0.98)	(1.90)	***				
	trust	3.22	4.70	4.00	-10.49	-1.48	-1.76	-1.20	-1.33
		(1.19)	(1.03)	(1.33)	***				
To help with a professional problem	use	3.47	5.40	4.49	-8.28	-1.93	-2.38	-1.47	-1.07
		(2.08)	(1.50)	(2.04)	***				
	trust	2.87	4.46	3.71	-10.22	-1.59	-1.90	-1.29	-1.30
		(1.28)	(1.17)	(1.46)	***				
To obtain health advice	use	2.90	3.97	3.47	-4.25	-1.06	-1.56	-0.57	-0.54
		(2.04)	(1.91)	(2.04)	***				

	trust	2.68 (1.46)	3.63 (1.39)	3.18 (1.49)	-5.25 ***	-0.95	-1.30	-0.59	-0.67
To facilitate a creative process	use	3.82 (2.09)	5.68 (1.44)	4.80 (2.00)	-8.11 ***	-1.87	-2.32	-1.41	-1.05
	trust	3.50 (1.45)	5.15 (1.20)	4.37 (1.56)	-9.79 ***	-1.65	-1.98	-1.32	-1.24
To support solving a personal or family problem	use	2.29 (1.82)	3.33 (1.99)	2.84 (1.98)	-4.27 ***	-1.04	-1.52	-0.56	-0.54
	trust	2.13 (1.23)	3.23 (1.47)	2.71 (1.46)	-6.39 ***	-1.09	-1.43	-0.76	-0.80
To support solving a problem of my community	use	2.75 (1.83)	4.16 (1.93)	3.49 (2.01)	-5.90 ***	-1.41	-1.88	-0.94	-0.75
	trust	2.58 (1.30)	3.94 (1.40)	3.30 (1.51)	-7.90 ***	-1.36	-1.70	-1.02	-1.00
For entertainment	use	3.84 (2.15)	5.26 (1.79)	4.59 (2.09)	-5.61 ***	-1.42	-1.92	-0.92	-0.72
	trust	3.62 (1.50)	5.03 (1.43)	4.37 (1.62)	-7.58 ***	-1.41	-1.78	-1.05	-0.96
For social companionship	use	2.38 (1.87)	2.77 (1.92)	2.59 (1.91)	-1.63 ns	-0.39	-0.87	0.08	-0.21
	trust	2.43 (1.44)	3.17 (1.62)	2.82 (1.58)	-3.80 ***	-0.74	-1.13	-0.36	-0.48
To support household tasks	use	3.87 (2.08)	5.04 (1.88)	4.49 (2.06)	-4.63 ***	-1.17	-1.67	-0.67	-0.59
	trust	3.87 (1.58)	4.85 (1.58)	4.39 (1.65)	-4.89 ***	-0.98	-1.38	-0.59	-0.62
To support a school or academic task	use	3.31 (1.90)	5.52 (1.27)	4.48 (1.94)	-10.66 ***	-2.21	-2.62	-1.80	-1.39
	trust	3.17 (1.45)	4.69 (1.19)	3.97 (1.52)	-9.07 ***	-1.52	-1.85	-1.19	-1.15
To make financial decisions	use	2.84 (1.96)	4.06 (1.93)	3.48 (2.04)	-4.96 ***	-1.23	-1.72	-0.74	-0.63
	trust	2.61 (1.30)	3.76 (1.52)	3.22 (1.53)	-6.33 ***	-1.14	-1.50	-0.79	-0.81

*: $p \leq 0.05$; **: $p \leq 0.01$; ***: $p \leq 0.001$

As shown in Table 3, Supporters and Critics also have different positions in terms of the likelihood that they would consider using AI and the level of trust they place in the information they obtain from AI. While Critics would not consider using AI for any of the proposed activities or trusting the information of AI, Supporters would consider the use for some activities, especially for gathering information on a topic of interest, to facilitate a creative process, for entertainment, but also for professional problems and academic tasks. However, overall respondents are less inclined to use AI, and trust the information obtained, for community or personal problems, financial or health advice. They also disregard social companionship, in line with the results found by Philipsen et al. (2022).

Compared with the answers on acceptability, the questions on eventual uses and trust of AI are more likely to elicit answers that are direct, individualized, and relate to potentially negative consequences. For example, AI is relatively trustworthy for entertainment or to facilitate creative processes, but less so in helping solve personal problems or to obtain health or financial advice. In agreement with Brauner et al. (2023), the results highlight that to achieve widespread adoption of AI technology, it is necessary to take into account perceptions and risk assessments at both the individual and societal levels.

Concerning knowledge about AI, of the presented AI tools, the most known and used is ChatGPT, with 54.2% of Supporters saying that they “have used it sometimes” and 53.8% of Critics selecting the option “I have heard about it, but I have never used it” (see Figure 2). Co-pilot and Gemini are also known mainly by Supporters, but less used.

Figure 2. Knowledge and experience of generative AI tools. Percentages by cluster

Results concerning the actual experience of use of AI tools show that the large majority (87.8%) of Supporters has already used generative AI tools, while only 43.6% of Critics admits to have done so, $\chi^2(1) = 52.52, p < .001$. Work purposes are mentioned by almost half of the participants (45.2%), by 23.9% of the Critics and 64.1% of Supporters, followed by leisure (Critics: 16.2%; Supporters: 36.6%; Total: 27.0%), education (Critics: 8.5%; Supporters: 37.4%; Total: 23.8%), and problem solving (Critics: 11.1%; Supporters: 32.8%; Total: 22.6%). Only a small minority used AI for health advice (Critics: 0.9%; Supporters: 10.7%; Total: 6.0%) or as social companions (Critics: 0.9%; Supporters: 2.3%; Total: 1.6%), which is in line with the levels of acceptability and trustworthiness.

In relation to the open question “*Of the things you have done using Artificial Intelligence, tell us about the one that you consider to be the most interesting*”, only 31.6% of Critics answered compared to 58.8% of Supporters. The type of activities was also slightly different, with Critics mentioning more sporadic use and trivial activities (e.g., food recipes) while for some of the Supporters AI is already a tool of daily use, used to help in daily tasks and work problems.

Virtual Assistants: manage schedules, answer questions both professionally and academically. Art and Music Creation: Image creation and musical composition. Data Analysis: Analyze visitor data to better understand visiting patterns and preferences. Translation and Accessibility: Machine translation and speech recognition tools. Academic Research: analysis of historical texts and documents, identifying patterns and connections that may not be evident at first glance. Educational Content Creation: developing personalized educational materials such as interactive quizzes and learning modules (Supporters, 487)

I just did this one: I created an image for my birthday party invitation (Critics, 318)

Use of AI: Need for Preparation and Regulation

Both Critics and Supporters strongly agree, to the same level, that preparation and specialised education is needed to deal with AI and use AI tools (Critics: 6.29; Supporters: 6.37; $t(246) = -.513, ns$), and with the need to regulate the use of AI (Critics: 6.61; Supporters: 6.51; $t(246) = .695, ns$). However, Supporters trust more than Critics in the trustworthiness of institutions like the European political institutions (Critics: 3.99;

Supporters: 5.09, $t(227.56) = -4.850$, $p < .001$, $d = -.623$, 95% CI [-1.55, -.65]); the National political institutions (Critics: 3.53; Supporters: 4.39; $t(246) = -3.888$, $p < .001$, $d = -.495$, 95% CI [-1.30, -.42]); Public institutions (Critics: 3.79; Supporters: 4.76; $t(246) = -4.715$, $p < .001$, $d = -.600$, 95% CI [-1.368, -.562]); and ONGs (Critics: 3.46; Supporters: 4.04, $t(246) = -2.702$, $p = .007$, $d = -.344$, 95% CI [-1.00, -.16]) to regulate AI. Supporters also distrust less than Critics on Tech companies (Critics: 2.38; Supporters: 3.49; $t(243.68) = -4.845$, $p < .001$, $d = -.612$, 95% CI [-1.56, -.65]), private enterprises (Critics: 2.29; Supporters: 2.78; $t(246) = -2.507$, $p = .013$, $d = -.319$, 95% CI [-.88, -.11]), and people in general (Critics: 2.44; Supporters: 3.14; $t(243.86) = -3.50$, $p < .001$, $d = -.441$, 95% CI [-1.09, -.30]). These opinions suggest an alignment with the survey by David and collaborators (2024), in the urgent need for regulation and acceptance of governmental involvement. Distinctively, both studies suggest that the public is less willing to entrust corporations and tech companies with the regulation of AI. Cuéllar and Huq (2002) have also shown that there are risks and benefits of (different kinds of) regulations and meta-regulation.

Positions on AI: Dimensions of Psychosocial Characterization

We have not found significant socio-demographic differences distinguishing the clusters of Critics and Supporters (see Appendix 1), nor in terms of the access to equipment, as support for AI is independent from having access or ownership ($p > .05$) of all devices mentioned (computer, laptop, tablet, smartphone, smartwatch). This may be due to the limitations of the small sample ($N=248$) and the relative homogeneity in terms of level of education and occupational situation, with underrepresentation of less educated and vulnerable social groups. However, the two groups differ on the self-assessment of expertise in using electronics, the internet, and AI tools. Critics perceived themselves as lacking the necessary knowledge to use AI tools and Supporters are somewhat ambivalent (Critics: 2.35; Supporters: 4.09, $t(246) = -9.668$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.230$, 95% CI [-2.097, -1.387]). Nevertheless, Supporters' responses indicate that they claim to have more expertise in the use of electronics (Critics: 5.33; Supporters: 5.78, $t(218.85) = -3.395$, $p < .001$, $d = -.438$, 95% CI [-.701, -.186]), and the internet (Critics: 5.46; Supporters: 5.92, $t(217.69) = -3.427$, $p < .001$, $d = -.442$, 95% CI [-.715, -.193]). These values tend to be higher than those of the Critics. For a more widespread use of AI, the results suggest that rather than promoting access to equipment, it is necessary to promote opportunities for education and knowledge development, not only about AI as mentioned before, but in tech more broadly. This will be fundamental to reduce the digital divide and the risk of escalating social inequalities (Wang et al., 2024).

Emotions can play an active role and contribute to the shaping of technological futures, particularly in contexts of uncertainty and ambivalence (Hughes, 2024). Not

surprisingly, AI elicits positive and negative emotions¹ to a different degree in Critics and Supporters. For Supporters, AI elicits mainly interest ($M=5.95$), excitement ($M=5.31$) and admiration ($M=5.20$), for Critics it elicits mostly fear ($M=4.84$). Moreover, Critics see AI mainly as a threat² while Supporters see it as an opportunity (Critics: 3.04; Supporters: 4.95; $t(246) = -11.66, p < .001, d = -1.48, 95\% \text{ CI } [-2.23, -1.59]$). However, both groups agree that for the older generations, AI is more a threat than an opportunity.

In terms of the salience of AI, Supporters tend to talk more frequently about AI than Critics (Critics: 2.78; Supporters: 3.93; $t(246) = -6.185, p < .001, d = -.787, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.523, -.787]$). Themes of the conversations are also slightly different with Supporters mentioning the applications, and pros and cons, of AI on work, education and health while Critics stress the risks, the (potential for) malpractices and the negative consequences for the future of humankind.

How it can help us do boring jobs (e.g., admin) faster (Supporters, 070)

How helpful is it versus how dangerous it is (Supporters, 098)

The possibility of AI being able to replace real human relationships, on the other hand the possibility of AI being able to play a leading role in healthcare, in diagnosing and preventing diseases and monitoring patients (Supporters, 659)

In general, the content of the conversations established is related to the rapid evolution and dangers of these tools (...) despite considering some benefits in terms of health or even security (...) it seems that we have reached the era of "Big Brother." Evolving, yes, but without it leading to the social and moral decline of humanity... it's scary! (Critics, 060)

The harms of AI and its misuse for fraudulent schemes (Critics, 490)

probably the possibility/ grim reality of the human race handing control to machines, then being deemed surplus to requirements and being taken out of equation (Critics, 050)

In terms of the dimensions valued in the information received, there are significant differences for the three dimensions extracted by the PCA (see Appendix 4), between Supporters and Critics. Supporters tend to value, more than Critics, dimensions which pertain to indicators of *Structural and Dynamic Complexity* (Critics: 5.61; Supporters: 6.01; $t(195.89) = -2.85, p < .010, d = -.37, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.69, -.12]$) of the thinking that underlies the information to them (cf. Melo, 2020), as well as *Causal Complexity* (Critics: 5.16; Supporters: 5.69; $t(196.30) = -3.92, p < .001, d = -.51, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.80, -.26]$) and *Simplicity of the Presentation of Information* (Critics: 3.67; Supporters: 4.47; $t(246) = -4.65, p < .001, d = -.59, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.14, -.46]$). Nevertheless the *Simplicity of the Presentation of Information* values are relatively moderate for both groups, they are lower for Critics. These findings

¹ Positive emotions (Critics: 2.89; Supporters: 4.85), $t(246) = 14.74, p < .001, d = 1.875, 95\% \text{ CI } [-2.23, -1.70]$; Negative emotions (Critics: 3.24; Supporters: 2.45), $t(246) = 5.67, p < .001, d = .722, 95\% \text{ CI } [.52, 1.08]$. Variables composed from the results of the principal component factor analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation (see Appendix 2).

² Variable resulting from the average of 7 items (for you personally, for the younger generations; for the older generations; for the country where you live; for poor and developing countries; for rich and developed countries; for the world in general) in a 7-point bipolar scale (1 = *threat*; 7 = *opportunity*) after the results of the principal component factor analysis with varimax rotation extracted only on factor explaining 69.887% of the total variance (see Appendix 3).

suggest the relevance of exploring further the connections between opinions of AI and the complexity of the modes of thinking.

Finally, we also explored (see Appendix 5) the extent to which the two groups had different perspectives on the functioning of society (anomie, system justification and legal cynicism) and different conceptions of distributive justice (equality, equity and need). The results revealed that only one dimension distinguishes the two: the extent to which they justify the status quo (Critics: 2.03; Supporters: 2.44; $t(246) = -2.70, p < .001, d = -.34, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.70, -.11]$), with Supporters less questioning of the current state of affairs than Critics. This result may also explain a more proactive, motivated attitude for dealing with the envisioned future.

Overall, findings suggest that the respondents' elicited emotions, representations and imagined futures are mainly drawn from a gap generated between those who have used AI tools and view themselves as more skilled and adapted to understanding the potential of AI, and those who have had less personal experience and, consequently, tend to express more cautious and wary opinions. However, the causal relationship was not possible to establish from the study. Moreover, differences in the level of acceptability of different uses, trust in institutions to regulate AI, along with differences in information processing and perceived possibilities of societal change, suggest that the determinants of positions are variegated and the interrelations between them may present complex arrangements.

Conclusive Remarks

The world is facing rapid, vast and profound societal transformations, some of which may be driven, or at least accelerated, by the recent developments in the field of AI. In the introduction to a special issue in *AI & Society*, Manyika (2022) poses the question “is it worth it? (AI)”. Upon reflecting on the current developments, challenges and potential for impact, they conclude with a conditional “yes”, to the extent that society manages to tackle four key issues, namely ensuring: powerful but safe AI, a focus on the greatest challenges, responsible development and governance, and the successful adaptation of society and its institutions. The attitudes, discourses and societal representations on AI will affect the way we cope with such challenges. This study, based on an online survey, aimed at exploring public opinion regarding AI and the use of AI. It showed that AI is associated mainly with the future of innovation in technology, robotics and computers. Two opposing positions were found: Supporters associate AI with potential benefits in line with technological optimism, like automation, speed and efficiency. Critics tend to fear AI, associated with the degradation of social and human values (e.g. trust, ethics). Support for AI is associated with more intensive uses of technology in daily lives. The respondents that admitted more familiarity and self-perception of a high level of expertise with technology in general tended to be more enthusiastic about AI in the future. Projection of beneficial uses of AI tends to favour large wide-impacting global and societal issues (e.g. climate change, health care), or smaller, more individual and less consequential tasks (e.g., entertainment).

Results also point towards some political implications of specialised education and regulation, which are considered essential by both Critics and Supporters. The capacity of national, European, and transnational political institutions to effectively regulate AI and promote AI literacy will likely affect the possible impacts of AI in the future of humankind, but also on the trust in those institutions themselves.

The study's small sample size and relative homogeneity in terms of the level of education and type of occupation limits generalization and calls for caution in interpreting the results. Further studies, conducted with more participatory and qualitative methodologies and that are able to reach social groups with less technological literacy, are needed to capture a broader picture of the opinions regarding AI and the challenges that this technological revolution will pose to humankind. Nonetheless, the findings highlight the relevance of deepening the assessment of the public's views and perceptions of AI, as it develops and pervades daily lives and the ways in which human beings relate to and connect to technology. Often lauded as a cutting-edge feature in state-of-the-art devices, or sometimes silently integrated into large-scale systems, AI seems to already have generated relevant social and cultural impacts.

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Appendix 1. Sociodemographic characterization. Percentages and chi-square values based on clusters.

	Critics (n=117)	Supporters (n=131)	Total (N=248)	χ^2
Gender				
Male	27.4%	37.4%	32.7%	2.25 ² <i>ns</i>
Female	70.1%	61.1%	65.3%	
Non-binary	2.6%	1.5%	2.0%	
Age group				
<=34 years	13.7%	11.5%	12.5%	0.40 <i>ns</i>
35-44 years	25.6%	24.4%	25.0%	
45-54 years	31.6%	33.6%	32.7%	
>=55 years	29.1%	30.5%	29.8%	
Education				
Basic education	0.9%	0.8%	0.8%	8.10 <i>ns</i>
Secondary education	30.8%	16.2%	23.1%	
Graduation	33.3%	39.2%	36.4%	
Master	18.8%	20.0%	19.4%	
PhD	16.2%	23.8%	20.2%	
Occupational situation				
Self-employed	5.1%	3.9%	4.5%	5.21 <i>ns</i>
Work for others with a contract/work of unlimited duration (permanent)	76.1%	79.1%	77.6%	
Working for others with a contract/work of limited duration (temporary)	6.8%	11.6%	9.3%	
Full time student	6.8%	2.3%	4.5%	
Retired	5.1%	3.1%	4.1%	
Family				
It's just me	12.0%	11.5%	11.7%	3.54 <i>ns</i>
It's me and my partner	17.1%	15.4%	16.2%	
It's me my partner and my children	27.4%	34.6%	31.2%	
It's me and my children	3.4%	5.4%	4.5%	
Other situation	33.3%	24.6%	28.7%	
No answer	6.8%	8.5%	7.7%	
Financial situation				
It pays without difficulty	29.9%	39.7%	35.1%	2.69 ³ <i>ns</i>
It pays, but from time to time it has difficulties	43.6%	38.9%	41.1%	

² χ^2 calculated without "non-binary"

It pays, but it's a constant struggle	21.4%	16.8%	19.0%	
Is having financial problems	0.9%	1.5%	1.2%	
No answer	4.3%	3.1%	3.6%	
Country of residence				
Portugal	85.5%	89.3%	87.5%	0.52
Other	14.5%	10.7%	12.5%	
Place of residence				
Country's capital	12.0%	9.9%	10.9%	4.21 <i>ns</i>
One of the largest cities in the country	14.5%	15.3%	14.9%	
The suburb of one of the largest cities in the country	19.7%	19.1%	19.4%	
In a medium sized city	28.2%	19.8%	23.8%	
In a village, small town or hamlet	24.8%	34.4%	29.8%	
No answer	0.9%	1.5%	1.2%	
Nationality				
Portuguese	85.3%	85.4%	85.4%	0.00 <i>ns</i>
Other	14.7%	14.6%	14.6%	

³ χ^2 calculated without the conditions "is having financial problems" and "no answer".

Appendix 2. Emotions elicited by AI (1 = *Not at all*; 7 = *Very much*). Factorial solution, percentages of variance explained by each component, as well as the internal consistency of the sub-scales constructed.

	Component	
	1	2
	30.09%	26.11%
	$\alpha = 0.90$	$\alpha = 0.80$
Joy	0.871	-0.001
Excitement	0.865	-0.226
Admiration	0.854	-0.219
Hope	0.829	-0.180
Serenity	0.723	-0.123
Interest	0.635	-0.230
Anger	-0.199	0.801
Sadness	-0.231	0.797
Hate	-0.178	0.759
Guilt	0.301	0.641
Disappointment	-0.226	0.596
Fear	-0.310	0.560

Appendix 3. AI: threat or opportunity (1 = *threat*; 7 = *opportunity*). Factorial solution, percentages of variance explained by each component, as well as the internal consistency of the sub-scales constructed.

	Component 1	Mean	Standard Deviation
	69.88%		
	$\alpha = .93$		
For the country where you live	0.927	4.10	1.87
For the world in general	0.922	4.03	1.87
For you personally	0.864	4.36	1.83
For the younger generations	0.851	4.19	2.14
For poor and developing countries	0.813	3.85	1.99
For rich and developed countries	0.769	4.53	1.99
For the older generations	0.677	3.30	1.76

Appendix 4. Evaluation of information (1=*I do not value at all*; 7=*I totally value*). Factorial solution, percentages of variance explained by each component, as well as the internal consistency of the sub-scales constructed.

	Component		
	1	2	3
	37.56 %	20.14 %	10.66 %
	$\alpha = .97$	$\alpha = .91$	$\alpha = .77$
<i>Structural and Dynamic Complexity</i>			
The information is strongly related and there is an exploration of relations between the theme/problem and its context	0.870	0.214	0.119
The existence of evidence that attests the information	0.837	0.220	0.040
The clarity of the intentionalities with which the information or knowledge can be used	0.836	0.290	0.084
The consideration of different aspects of the context (historical, temporal, situational) of the theme	0.831	0.227	0.053
The theme/problem is approached considering the perspectives of the different entities involved or affected by the problem (e.g. people, institutions, nature)	0.824	0.361	0.091
The clarity of the values at stake or that can be affected by the theme/problem are clarified	0.795	0.341	0.093
The consideration of potential implications and consequences, positive and negative, of that knowledge or information about the theme/problem are considered.	0.795	0.321	0.013
The variety of types and/or sources of information	0.782	0.148	0.169
The consideration of the way the theme/problem has varied through time	0.770	0.350	0.063
Consideration of the relations between the different entities involved in the theme/problem and of how they may affect the theme/problem	0.765	0.437	0.032
Consideration of how the problem may appear differently with different timescales (e.g. when one looks for the perspective of a day, a month, a year, decades or millennia)	0.757	0.376	0.132
The presentation is rich in details	0.703	0.259	0.158
<i>Causal Complexity</i>			
The information or knowledge can be updated or corrected	0.201	0.775	0.142
The extent to which the information or knowledge considers the way how people and other entities (e.g. nature) can be affected and how they see themselves in the relation with a theme/ problem	0.473	0.718	0.076
The explanations consider the way that different elements are interconnected and mutually affect each other (e.g. A leads to B that affects A; or A leads to B and leads to C which affects A)	0.479	0.653	0.095
The explanations consider unexpected or difficult to anticipate dimensions	0.196	0.626	0.342
The information or knowledge has some pragmatic utility and can be applied or can guide actions or decisions	0.347	0.623	0.369
The extent to which the explanations simultaneously focus the basic elements that compose the problem the problem as a whole and their relation.	0.487	0.618	0.081
The explanations look at the “whole” of the problem and its totality	0.496	0.564	0.180
The explanations are focused on the characteristics of the most basic elements that compose the theme/problem and try to divide it into parts	0.275	0.524	0.425
Clear causes and effects are presented and directly linked (e.g. of the type A leads to B)	0.432	0.509	0.246
<i>Simplicity of the Presentation of Information</i>			
The presentation is focused on the theme/problem and leaves out details of the context of what is around	0.005	0.049	0.875
The presentation is synthetic and only focus the more relevant parts	0.102	0.182	0.820

The information and the knowledge “looks nice” and has harmony or internal coherence	0.064	0.345	0.658
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Appendix 5. Perspectives on Society and Justice Principles. Means Based on Clusters, Standard Deviations in Parentheses.

	Critics	Supporters	Total	<i>t</i>	Mean difference	95% CI		Cohen's <i>d</i>
	(n=117)	(n=131)	(N=248)	sig		Inf.	Sup.	
<i>Perspectives on Society</i>								
Anomie ⁴	3.84	3.78	3.81	.31	.05	-.28	.39	.04
	(1.32)	(1.35)	(1.33)	<i>ns</i>				
System justification ⁵	2.03	2.44	2.25	-2.70	-.40	-.70	-.11	-.34
	(1.12)	(1.22)	(1.19)	**				
Legal cynicism	2.55	2.30	2.42	1.62	.25	-.05	.55	.21
	(1.17)	(1.22)	(1.20)	<i>ns</i>				
<i>Justice Principles</i>								
Equality	5.20	4.95	5.07	1.09	.25	-.20	.71	.14
	(1.86)	(1.78)	(1.82)	<i>ns</i>				
Equity	4.63	4.77	4.70	-.71	-.15	-.56	.26	-.09
	(1.63)	(1.64)	(1.63)	<i>ns</i>				
Need	5.32	5.26	5.29	.32	.06	-.33	.46	.04
	(1.61)	(1.54)	(1.57)	<i>ns</i>				

*: $p \leq 0.05$; **: $p \leq 0.01$; ***: $p \leq 0.001$

⁴ Translated and adapted to Portuguese from McClosky, H. & Schaar, J. H. (1965). Psychological dimensions of anomie. *American Sociological Review*, 30, 14-40.

⁵ Selected items translated and adapted to Portuguese from Kay, A. C., & Jost, J. T. (2003). Complementary justice: Effects of "poor but happy" and "poor but honest" stereotype exemplars on system justification and implicit activation of the justice motive. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 85(5), 823-837. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.85.5.823>